

How can we improve our English skills?

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Abstract: If we understand how to significantly improve our English per week, we will solve many problems in life. Almost all of us need to know English. But no one wants to spend a lot of time and effort to learn the language. Learning English on Skype is surely the most popular and affordable way and material costs. Most people understand that learning a language is a long and time-consuming process. This article covers how to improve our knowledge of English.

Keywords: English, skill, result, language, vocabulary, learning, experience.

"We all encounter obstacles to learning a language. Sometimes you want to remove everything. And this is true for any field. But tell me, you will never stop speaking Russian and make it Can't you listen? Of course not. For us, Russian is just a tool. So English is also a tool. Forget sitting for a dictionary. Fantasize and think. You won't spoil anything. But you know the whole world . Remove the barriers, remove the fear. Just dive into it with your head. From now on forever, you will engage in our language, only when you want to. Only when your natural curiosity awakens. The rest of the time, the language is really worth it. tool to do. With something like this. I love it to talk to my students: "Kaifui, Lech, just kaifui!"

And now it's time for real action. It's always interesting to read other stories, but often you don't know where to start. Below I describe the actions that I want you

to do on the way cepete dream Mastering English. That's right! Get ready for a week of challenges!

To improve your English significantly in a week, do the following:

And now time is moving. Go ahead! Dare to! One week a week is a new world - the Internet, podcast, TV, sewing commission and more that you listen to on the way to work. Try it in English. Just relax and enjoy. Want to work for yourself.

At the same time, constant management:

- His thoughts, internal communication. Try to think in English. But at the same time non-violent. When you think in Russian, translate the above phrase into English and continue to live))

- What is Google? At first I don't want to do it in English at all, but believe me, there is a gap. You understand 80% of the information available. In life, some of us do not look at the remaining 20. Yes, and is it necessary? So, no excuses and no moves, no moves. "How to use a toothbrush?", "How to use a toothbrush?", "How to find a cute guy in Berlin?" And "How to find a handsome guy in Berlin?" That's all. Very easy.

At the end of the week, just look around and look back. You've spent the entire week absolutely drowning in language. Fifteen years ago, someone could only dream about this. There were no such features. We have this. It helps me. During this time, I moved the barrier at a high level and calmly. I say the words, pull the grammar in the mood. How much do I plan to learn the language? Yes, I mastered it, advanced to intermediate. For me, language should be a tool to achieve other goals for communication. Subjects, God will give after 20 years, maybe ahead, I will not be separated from the mother tongue. This is not

satisfactory. Now you have a choice. Join in!

This is probably everyone. In conclusion, I would like to say that all of the above is for entertainment and not to think about anything else. It's not. The purpose of this article is a specific call to action. Call to call and change your approach, understand in practice - you need to learn something in English this week. You can read hundreds of messages, learn something from them, and you can get it once and for all. In the modern world, where there is a great demand for the English language and for professionals who master it well, comprehensive learning of it requires careful formation of all skills.

In order to master English at or near the level of native speakers, teachers will have to organize exercises, assignments and lessons aimed at mastering all language skills in the educational process and play the role of a facilitator (assistant) rather than a traditional teacher in the language learning process. These language skills are: listening, speaking, reading, writing. Each of these skills is important to achieving the desired goal of language learning. Therefore, their mastery and development remains one of the necessary tasks of today. Listening comprehension and reading are considered passive (receptive) skills, because they do not create language material, but rather, they help to receive material created by others. Speaking and writing are active (creative) skills, because students express their thoughts in the form of oral or written sentences with the help of language material. Thus, active and passive skills are not displayed at the same time. Listening is required before speaking, reading before writing (or vice versa). If the language learner does not fully master each and use their capabilities properly, he

may not be able to achieve the intended goal. At the same time, students should consider them equally important, because each of them is a separate, independent phenomenon related to language learning. In addition, teachers should use modern and advanced pedagogical technologies, methods and approaches in their lessons.

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